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FACTORS INFLUENCING MENTAL HEALTH IN A CARDIAC POPULATION

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By

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ABSTRACT

Early screening of depressive symptoms in a patient that is beginning a cardiac rehabilitation (CR) program may provide an opportunity for ongoing assessment and support. Identifying depression in cardiac patients may benefit both the physical and mental health and prevent worsening of cardiac disease. The purpose of this study was to identify demographic characteristics that may be related to the mental health status of cardiac patients, and to examine the effect of participation in CR on mental health.

A retrospective review of data from patients who participated in a CR program between 2008-2010 was evaluated. Demographic data, including age, gender, cardiac diagnosis or intervention were used to describe the sample and then analyzed for an association with a low MCS score (< 45), which may indicate depression. Pre and post cardiac rehabilitation MCS scores were analyzed for statistically significant differences. No statistically significant association was identified between a low MCS score and the demographic factors analyzed. There was a statistically significant increase in MCS scores in patients that had completed the 12-week CR program ($M_{\text{MCS Pretest}} = 51.25$, $SD = 10.15$; $M_{\text{MCS Posttest}} = 53.79$, $SD = 8.48$; $t(214) = -3.87$, $p < .001$). The MCS score calculated from the SF12 may provide additional data for identifying patients at risk for depression in a cardiac population. Careful assessment for mental health problems as well as participation in a CR program may make a difference in mental health status, and may have a positive impact on clinical outcomes for this group.

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BACKGROUND

Problem Statement

Cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of death for both men and women, and accounts for approximately 30% of deaths annually in the United States (World Health Organization, 2013). Greater than one in three adults have some form of cardiovascular disease (Go et al., 2013). Since 1984, the number of deaths related to cardiovascular disease in women has exceeded the number in men; however, the incidence of this disease remains higher in the male population (Roger et al., 2012).

When a cardiac event occurs, depression is often a resulting symptom that may have a significant impact on psychological health (Rutledge et al., 2012). How a person perceives his/her own health can be disrupted by a cardiovascular event or diagnosis and change an individual's quality of life (Yohannes, Doherty, Bundy, & Yalfani, 2010). Depression also affects quality of life (Grace, Grewal, Arthur, Abramson, & Stewart, 2008). In addition to impacting a person's quality of life, depression is linked to both the development and worsening of cardiovascular disease (Rutledge et al., 2012). In fact, depression has been associated with increasing mortality as much as two to four times in the cardiac patient population (Sherwood, Hinderliter, Watkins, Waugh, & Blumenthal, 2005).

In the general population, depression occurs approximately two times more often in women than in men (Barth et al., 2009; Frasure-Smith & Lesperance, 2005).

Depression itself has been identified as a risk factor for cardiac disease (Rutledge et al., 2012; Voss, Boettger, Schultz, Gross, & Karl-Jurgen, 2011; Whang et al., 2009).

Identifying patients with mental health problems such as depression, then providing

resources and implementing interventions such as cardiac rehabilitation (CR) may improve depression symptoms and improve cardiovascular health status.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this study is to describe mental health in a population of cardiac patients. Other purposes are to identify factors associated with mental health problems, and assess the effect of CR on mental health.

Research Questions

For the purpose of this study, the following questions will be addressed:

1. What is the mental health status among a population of cardiac patients participating in a cardiac rehabilitation program?
2. What factors are associated with mental health problems in a cardiac patient population?
3. What is the effect of participation in a cardiac rehabilitation program on mental health?

Theoretical Framework

The Theory of Symptom Management Model was originally developed in 1994 by the University of California, San Francisco School of Nursing Symptom Management Faculty Group, and was revised by Dodd et al. in 2001. The influence of the individual, environment and the domains of health and illness were included in the 2001 revision, bringing the concepts together to form the current conceptual framework of the model. Since 2001, this theory has been studied and tested in a variety of patient populations, and is now identified as a middle-range theory as opposed to its initial origins as a simple model (Humphreys et al., 2008). This theory provides a structure by which nurses can

better understand patient symptom experiences, and may be used to influence the care management of patients who have symptomatic cardiac disease.

The Theory of Symptom Management focuses on the effect symptoms exert on the patient. Using this theory as a framework, nurses are enabled to more fully understand the patient's experiential perception of the symptom, its meaning, and his/her response to the symptom (the outcome). The theory allows the nurse to study a symptom from both the subjective and objective perspectives. In addition, this theory can be useful in planning interventions based on three dimensions: (a) the symptom experience; (b) the symptom management; and, (c) the symptom outcome (Larson et al., 1994).

A *symptom* is what a patient experiences; the self-report is the gold standard for understanding the individual's perception (Dodd et al., 2001). This perception includes judgments related to the patient's current feelings compared to the patient's usual state of health, and may be influenced by the social and cultural beliefs of that person. Also, the patient interprets how the symptom is experienced in terms of cause, effect, and severity. Thus, management begins with an assessment of the patient's perception of the particular symptom (Larson et al., 1994).

A patient's response to a symptom may include thoughts and feelings related to his/her perception about the meaning of the symptom (Dodd et al., 2001). Planning individualized care is dependent on this interpretation by the patient. The quality of one's life may not be negatively impacted if a person interprets a symptom as minor or of short duration. However, if the symptom persists for a prolonged period of time, the patient may become distressed and his/her quality of life may be affected (Larson et al., 1994).

The Theory of Symptom Management has several assumptions. The first assumption is related to the patient's perception and self-report of the experienced symptom. The first part of managing a symptom is to assess the patient's perception and meaning. Following a thorough assessment, an intervention and evaluation can be successfully designed (Larson et al., 1994). The second assumption includes consideration of a potential symptom. Although the symptom may not yet be experienced, the individual may assume a probable risk. The latter fact creates an opportunity to implement a primary prevention plan to better maintain the patient's health status (Dodd et al., 2001).

The third assumption refers to those patients who are not verbally expressive. In this situation, the caregiver or nurse is able to identify and intervene to manage the symptom. The fourth assumption is related to patient-centered management strategies. The plan needs to focus on the patient, the family, and the environment. The fifth assumption is related to symptom management. This particular process is individually modified and based on the person's outcomes as influenced by the person, his/her health or illness, or the environment (Dodd et al., 2001).

The Theory of Symptom Management encompasses three dimensions: the symptom experience, strategies for management, and the patient outcomes. Each person responds to a symptom based on individual maturity, gender, or other demographic, psychological, physiological, or sociological variables (Dodd et al., 2001; Humphreys et al., 2008; Larson et al., 1994). People evaluate symptoms and assign meaning by making judgments about how the symptom affects them. This evaluation and response can make a difference in the manner a person interprets the symptom (Dodd et al., 2001). Patients

are anxious about a symptom; this anxiety may alter their perception and experience of the symptom. Other patients may interpret the meaning of symptoms and experience depression as an outcome.

In 2001, when the theory was revised, the following nursing domains were included: the person, the health status, the illness, and the patient's environment. Within the *person domain*, one considers each individual's response to a symptom, the perception of the experience, and the level of the patient's maturity or development (Dodd et al., 2001). Demographic factors, such as age and gender, may also impact the perception and the meaning of a symptom.

After a cardiac event, patients may experience both psychological and physiologic changes. These patients may regard their health status as having been altered due to episodes of pain or fatigue. The perception of a particular symptom is different for each patient (Barth et al., 2009). A nurse may consider each of these influencing factors and plan care strategies to help patients through the experience.

Within the *health and illness* domain exists the consideration of each individual's level of health potential/actual risk factors, injuries and presenting disabilities. Assessment of influencing factors that affect a person's perceptions, evaluation, and response to a symptom or potential symptom is a significant component of the theory (Dodd et al., 2001). The *environment domain* includes the context in which the symptom occurs. The variables in the environment include the physical environment, social support, cultural beliefs, values, and practices. These factors may influence a patient's symptom experience and need to be evaluated when planning care (Dodd et al., 2001).

The Theory of Symptom Management provides a framework for understanding these concepts and the interconnection between them. The theory also provides guidance for the nurse in planning interventions and evaluating outcomes when working with various patient populations (Humphreys et al., 2008). In the cardiac patient population, individuals may respond to an unexpected symptom with episodes of depression or anxiety based on the assigned meaning and interpretation of the experience. A nurse working with cardiac patients may provide education and assist patients in expressing feelings about their symptom experiences. Nurses are in a opportune position to educate patients about symptoms that need to be reported versus those that are considered as normal symptoms of healing following a cardiac event (Yohannes et al., 2010).

The interrelated theoretical dimensions of the *symptom experience*, the *symptom management*, and the *outcome* can be applied to patients with cardiac problems. Gaining an understanding of how a patient may experience a symptom or a group of symptoms after a cardiac event may help nurses intervene more effectively. Considering a patient's self-report and identifying variables that may affect each individual might allow the nurse to more fully assess and treat the patient's symptom experience. Cardiac rehabilitation offers a safe and supervised setting in which a patient can stretch and strengthen muscles, build endurance while avoiding the symptoms of fatigue and pain. Nurses working with patients in a CR program have the opportunity to assess, intervene, and evaluate symptom experiences throughout the time of participation, and the Theory of Symptom Management provides structure for more planning and delivering optimum care.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Research Terms and Data Bases Searched

The literature review was performed via several databases including CINAHL, PubMed, PsycINFO, and EBSCO. The search was conducted using key words including: depression, cardiac disease, women, gender, age, heart disease, cardiovascular, Short Form 12 (SF12), Short Form 36 (SF36), quality of life, exercise, CR, coronary, myocardial infarction, coronary heart disease, benefits of CR, and CR program requirements.

Studies Utilizing the Theory of Symptom Management

In 2008, Humphreys et al. identified the Symptom Management Model as a theory and discussed its application in many patient populations. The use of the theory was described in many studies that supported the relationships of the concepts for use in research and practice. The Model or Theory of Symptom Management has been used frequently with patients suffering chronic conditions, including patients with cardiac disease. In one study, the theory was utilized to describe the symptom experience with patients who had undergone a coronary bypass grafting surgical procedure. The theory provided a framework for researchers to test an instrument called the Cardiac Symptom Survey that evaluated symptoms that patients experienced after cardiac surgery (Nieveen, Zimmerman, Barnason, & Yates, 2008).

Caldwell and Miaskowski (2000) studied the symptom experience of women with angina to identify areas for further research in understanding and planning strategies to manage this symptom. The concept of *symptom experience* from the theory provided structure in which to explore and understand the women's perceptions, evaluation, and

the response to experiencing angina, including how the symptom affected quality of life. The researchers discussed the importance of understanding an individual's perception of angina symptoms to more fully identify when a person would seek medical care.

Wongpiriyayothar, Piamjariyakul, and Williams (2011) utilized this theory to help guide the management of symptoms experienced with heart failure in a patient population living in Thailand. The Theory of Symptom Management assisted both patients and researchers to better understand the experiences of dyspnea and physical functioning in order to evaluate an educational intervention for these individuals. The three main concepts of the theory: (a) symptom experience; (b) symptom management; and (c) outcomes provided clarity to help patients and nurses better monitor and understand heart failure symptoms, provided guidance in developing individualized management strategies, and determined how to best evaluate the outcomes of interventions.

Eller et al. (2005) applied the Theory of Symptom Management to persons infected with human immunodeficiency virus. Citing evidence that depression may influence this disease progression, the researchers sought to identify self-care strategies based on the patient's own symptom experience. The patients were asked to describe how these strategies helped them manage their depressive symptoms. The researchers used the model to describe the dimensions of the symptom experience of depression.

Ahlberg, Ekman, Wallgren, and Gaston-Johansson (2004) utilized the Theory of Symptom Management to look at the quality of life and symptom distress experience in patients with uterine cancer. The authors of this study used the theory to evaluate the patient's experience of fatigue in order to guide treatment strategies. The theory provided

a framework for listing variables associated with contributing to fatigue in this population.

Gender Influences in Depression

Gender may potentially influence cardiac disease. Heart disease is the leading cause of mortality in both men and women (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2012; Go et al., 2013). Cardiovascular disease is associated with both physical and emotional stress that may result in patients experiencing anxiety and depression, and even more so in female patients (Frasure-Smith & Lesperance, 2008; Rutledge et al., 2012). Frasure-Smith and Lesperance (2008) studied women with acute coronary syndrome (ACS) for over two years, and found that they experienced depression at a higher rate (13.5%) than men (5.5%; $p < .001$). Major depression after coronary artery bypass grafting surgery occurs frequently, with women being at higher risk for depression than men (Doering, Cross, Magsarili, Howitt, & Cowan, 2007).

In general, depression occurs twice as frequently in females than in males. Women with cardiac disease have poorer psychosocial well-being than men with cardiovascular problems. Women appear to have more depression after a cardiac event than men (Grace et al., 2008). Women with high depression scores are less likely to be married, be less educated, and of non-white ethnicity. Doering et al. (2011) identified that women with cardiac disease also perceive that they have little control over their own health. In women with suspected myocardial ischemia, depression symptoms were common and associated with a higher cardiovascular risk factor status (Rutledge et al., 2012). Hunt-Shanks, Blanchard, and Reid (2009) identified that female cardiac patients

had higher scores than men for anxiety, depression, negative affect, and reduced exercise during each time interval measured over 24 months.

Assessing demographic factors, such as gender, may help the nurse individualize symptom management when planning care. Beckie, Beckstead, Schocken, Evans, and Fletcher (2011) found that women who participated in a modified, all-women CR program for reducing depressive symptoms showed significant improvement. The researchers identified social support from other females as an associated variable affecting their improvement in depression scores. In addition, the women who participated continued to experience fewer depressive symptoms for up to six months after discharge from the program. In an earlier study, Beckie and Beckstead (2010) examined the quality of life in women participating in a CR program. In this study, the researchers provided gender-specific exercise, motivational interviewing, and social support geared toward females. The results showed significantly improved quality of life scores. The women experienced benefits up to the time they were tested six months later. Gender may be an important factor to consider when planning care for cardiac patients. Nurses, considering the environmental factors while planning care, may make a positive difference in psychological as well as physical symptoms.

Women have higher incidences of depression and mortality with cardiac events and may have different experiences and benefits from participating in a CR program compared to men. In a study of 157 women with cardiac disease that participated in a CR program, researchers reported that women had improved quality of life scores and continued their exercise behavior for 18 months after program completion. The female

participants reported significant increases in physical quality of life and improvement in anxiety symptoms (Grace et al., 2008).

Cardiac Diagnoses and Interventional Procedure Influences

Studies that evaluated depressive symptoms among patients with cardiac diagnoses or cardiac interventional procedures were limited. Some mild differences in depressive symptoms were identified when looking at studies that specifically evaluated different patient populations, but these were inconsistent. Lesperance, Frasura-Smith, Talajic, and Bourassa (2002) found no difference in depressive symptoms between patients with myocardial infarctions, following angioplasties or cardiac surgeries. However, mild differences in depression levels between these categories were found in other studies (Milani & Lavie, 2007; Milani, Lavie, & Cassidy, 1996; Murphy et al., 2008). Variations between cardiac procedures or diagnoses and depressive symptoms may be a variable that could be evaluated further. If significant, individuals with certain cardiac diagnoses or interventional procedures could be more carefully monitored for symptoms of depression during the CR program. Marital status, age, obesity, and physical health summary scores may additionally have an impact on depression in women with cardiac disease. One or more of these factors have been included in a few studies, and may be significant when correlated with cardiac diagnosis or procedures (Beckie et al., 2011; Scotto, Waechter, & Rosneck, 2011).

Gravelly-Witte, De Gucht, Heiser, Grace, and Van Elderen (2007) identified that patients with a cardiac history experienced depression up to six months after an event. The researchers also found that patients who experienced angina after their cardiac event had much higher depression scores when evaluated six months later. This is significant

as the researchers identified that angina symptoms and depression influence each other, and angina was worsened by depression.

In a meta-analysis of 36 studies the evaluated the prevalence, interventions, and clinical outcomes of patients with heart failure and depression, significant depression was present in at least 21.5% of patients with heart failure. This depressed heart failure population had higher rates of mortality than heart failure patients without depression. The researchers identified that patients with more advanced heart failure had higher depression rates than patients with milder symptoms (Rutledge, Reis, Linke, Greenberg, & Mills, 2006).

Effect of Depression on Cardiac Risk

Assessing the cardiac patient's psychosocial status is important because depression has been associated with cardiovascular disease and may be a risk factor for a poor prognosis after a cardiac event (Sherwood et al., 2005; Voss et al., 2011; Whang et al., 2009). In 2008, the American Heart Association (AHA) recommended that depression and anxiety screening with intervention should be included in CR programs (Lichtman et al., 2008). Major depressive disorders have been identified as being present in approximately 20% of patients with cardiovascular disease. Elderon, Smolderen, Na, and Whooley (2011) found that participants who screened positive for depression showed a higher risk of cardiovascular events that could not be explained by common risk factors or demographics. Mental health screening may identify patients at higher risk for adverse cardiac events and prevention or treatment strategies may be implemented for this population.

Depression may result in physiological changes that are linked to cardiovascular disease. People experiencing depressive symptoms have a statistically lower life expectancy due to the autonomic state experienced during depression (Hunt-Shanks et al., 2009). Sherwood et al., (2005) found that depression was associated with a two to four times higher risk of mortality if present in a person with cardiovascular disease. In this study, patients with cardiovascular disease, as well as depression symptoms, showed signs of impaired endothelial function. The impaired endothelial function was evaluated by identifying decreased blood flow in a vessel, and was measured by brachial artery flow mediated dilation, an assessment of endothelial function. The study participants also showed higher low density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol levels, increased inflammation, and hypercoagulability. These findings were concerning as impaired endothelial function is both a cardiac risk factor and also an independent predictor of myocardial infarction. Impaired endothelial function is also associated with fatal myocardial infarction in a five-year follow-up period (Sherwood et al., 2005).

Voss et al. (2011) found mild differences in blood pressure measurements in women who were depressed when compared with women who were not. Depression was associated with changes in heart rate, blood pressure, and stimulation of the sympathetic branch of the nervous system suggesting an increased potential for arrhythmias. In another study by Frasure-Smith and Lesperance (2005), women showed a twofold increase in depression within the cardiac patient population when compared to the general population. This study compared 64 other studies that identified an association of depression as a risk factor for either developing or worsening cardiovascular disease.

Rutledge et al. (2012) found that modifiable risk factors for cardiovascular disease, such as obesity, were related to depression, and suggested that depression may have an impact on cardiovascular disease, with or without other known risk factors. The large number of studies associating depression with worsening cardiac disease was strong enough evidence to cause the AHA to recommend routine depression screening among cardiac patients (Lichtman et al., 2008).

Benefits of Cardiac Rehabilitation

A cardiac rehabilitation (CR) program is often available to patients with a diagnosed cardiac disease. A CR program includes education, counseling, psychosocial assessment, and cardiac risk modification along with prescribed exercise to strengthen and improve physical stamina (Balady et al., 2007; Braun, Wenger, & Rosenson, 2013). These programs focus on reconditioning the cardiovascular system so that patients may return to active and productive lives. These objectives are the basis of CR programs, and Medicare part B pays for 36 sessions. However, up to a 20% co-payment may be required (Medicare.gov, 2014). In addition, participation in these CR programs empowers the patients to take charge of their own health, and offers opportunities for education about disease progression and prevention for both patients and their families. In addition, exercise and progressive strengthening of muscles and stamina has been shown to improve overall emotional health (Blumenthal et al., 2012; Turner et al., 2010). In one study by Milani and Lavie (2007), the incidence of depressive symptoms decreased to 63% in a group of patients with coronary disease, from 17% at the beginning of CR, to 6% after completing the program ($n = 522, p < .0001$). Even mild improvements in fitness levels were associated with improved depressive symptoms.

The CR program can be tailored to meet individual needs and goals that benefit the patient. The guidelines required by the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) are based on core components from the National Quality Forum's "Preferred Practices and Performance Measures for Measuring and Reporting Care Coordination: A consensus report" (Balady et al., 2007). Certified CR programs are required to evaluate patient outcomes by standards established by the American Association of Cardiovascular and Pulmonary Rehabilitation (AACVPR).

Cardiac rehabilitation programs provide psychological support as well as the opportunity to exercise. The CR program generally requires two to three sessions per week of supervised exercise lasting up to one hour, plus diet and stress management education (Barth et al., 2009). Patients are monitored 36 times over a period of approximately twelve weeks by a multidisciplinary team. Patients receive emotional support and often bond with other patients during their program (Turner et al., 2010).

Cardiac rehabilitation programs have demonstrated an increase in overall health and wellness of the participants. The programs have an impact on the attitudes and mental health of patients exercising and participating in such a program (Davidson et al., 2008; Milani & Lavie, 2007; Shepherd & While, 2012; Turner et al., 2010). In a systematic review of 16 studies, Sherwood et al. (2005) identified improved quality of life as an outcome when CR was the intervention. Studies showed significant improvement associated with CR, both in physical as well as psychological quality of life scores. In another study, the researchers identified that health-related quality of life scores were higher when patients reported greater physical functionality. However, those with low exercise capability at the beginning of a CR program made the highest improvement in

their quality of life scores upon completion (Frank, McConnell, Rawson, & Fradkin, 2011).

Blumenthal et al. (2012) identified that exercise training was as effective at improving depressive symptoms as taking antidepressant medications. Antidepressant medications may have adverse side effects, such as, fatigue and sexual dysfunction. Exercise does not have these side effects and may improve the feeling of health. Supervised aerobic exercise, as part of the CR program, may then be effective in treating depression.

Several studies have demonstrated extended benefits for participants of cardiac rehabilitation programs. Scotto et al. (2011) determined that patients retained the information about diet and exercise as well as maintained exercise tolerance two months after completing the CR program. In the study by Milani et al. (1996), patients who were identified as depressed had a lower exercise capacity at baseline. After participation in a cardiac rehabilitation program, these participants had improved significantly in their depression scores as well as their quality of life scores. The researchers concluded that depression was decreased in patients enrolled in the 12-week, 36-visit cardiac rehabilitation program.

Cardiac Rehabilitation programs provide an opportunity for a patient to be assessed for depression and physical strength at continued and frequent intervals. Early indication of depressive symptoms in a patient that is beginning a CR program may provide an opportunity for ongoing assessment and support as these patients have 36 visits with CR nursing staff. Interventions aimed specifically towards assisting patients with these symptoms may make a significant difference in their quality of life.

Exercise and Age Influencing Factors in Depression

Exercise has been found to mitigate depressive symptoms in both genders (Hunt-Shanks et al., 2009). Yohannes et al. (2010) identified that anxiety and depression scores significantly improved from baseline at four different measurement points over 12 months following a CR program. On follow-up, 71% of patients were still exercising regularly at 12 months after completing the program. Female patients who exercised also scored higher on quality of life surveys (Yohannes et al., 2010).

Exercise has also been shown to have a positive impact on emotions consistent across various ranges of age. In a study examining both older and younger adults, a 15-minute moderate intensity exercise of stationary cycling resulted in improved emotions and affect, as well as in memory tests in both groups overall. In the older age group, the participants reported a greater feeling of calm after the exercise session when compared to their baseline (Carstensen, Hogan, & Matta, 2013).

Depression may hinder the effectiveness of a CR program as studies have shown that depressed patients have poorer attendance at these programs. In fact, patients with depressive symptoms have a five-fold risk of non-completion (Beckie et al., 2011). This is significant as in the study by Milani and Lavie (2007), depressed patients who completed CR had a 73% lower mortality (8% versus 30%; $p = .0005$) when compared with a control group of depressed patients that did not complete.

The influence of age on depression has had inconsistent results. Murphy et al. (2008) found no significant age differences in patterns of depression; however, other research found younger patients had higher depression and/or anxiety levels as

compared to older patients (Blumenthal et al., 2003; Elderon et al., 2011; Frasure-Smith & Lesperance, 2008).

Measuring Depression and Quality of Life

The Short Form 12 (SF12) is one instrument that is used to measure quality of life in both the physical and mental health areas. This self-administered questionnaire was developed by Ware, Kosinski, and Keller (1996), and has been widely used as a screening tool in the cardiac patient population to evaluate the perceptions of the patient regarding quality of life (Frank et al., 2011; Grace et al., 2008). The SF12 is a shortened version of the longer SF36, and has established reliability and validity when compared to the SF36 (Ware et al., 1996).

Use of the SF12 to Screen for Mental Health Issues

Commonly used depression screening instruments include the Beck Depression Inventory, the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale, and Hospital Depression and Anxiety Rating Scale. Very few studies have evaluated how well the SF12 performs when screening for mental disorders as it is considered a quality of life survey (Ware et al., 1996). Although the SF12 has been used extensively to evaluate quality of life in many patient populations, recent studies have utilized this instrument to screen for mental health problems.

The Mental Health Component Summary (MCS) score calculated from the SF12 has been identified as a valid measure of mental health and a screening tool that is useful in evaluating mental health status (Gill, Butterworth, Rodgers, & Mackinnon, 2007; Vilagut et al., 2013). In the study by Gill et al. (2007), the SF12 was used to identify patients with depression, anxiety, or both. The study's purpose was to evaluate the use of

this instrument and compare the performance against other screening measurements of mental health. In addition, the investigators sought to identify an appropriate cut-off score when screening for depression and anxiety. The cutoff chosen for identifying depression in this population was 45 or less out of 100, with 0.87 sensitivity and 0.83 specificity when compared to the other instruments (Gill et al., 2007). The researchers compared the MCS from the SF12 to several instruments and scoring methods including the RAND MHC-12, an alternative scoring method for the MCS by Hays (as cited in Vilagut et al., 2013), and found that these two questionnaires were able to identify depression equally. Further comparisons of different instruments revealed that the MCS was a better measure than the General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-12), and equal in accuracy to the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K-6) in identifying depression (Gill et al., 2007).

In a more recent study by Vilagut et al. (2013), the MCS, from the SF12, was assessed as a screening instrument specifically for depression, and did not assess for anxiety. In this study, three different scoring methods of this tool were evaluated. The data came from the European Study of the Epidemiology of Mental Disorders using the SF12 questionnaire ($n = 21,425$). The three algorithms used to score the mental component summary measure including the original method created by the authors of the SF12 (Ware et al., 1996), the RAND-12 Mental Health Composite, and the Bi-dimensional Response Process Model (BRP-12 MHS), another scoring method proposed by Forero (as cited in Vilagut et al., 2013). These scores were correlated using a diagnostic interview process and version 3.0 of the World Health Organization Composite International Diagnostic Interview that follows DSM-IV and ICD-10 criteria. To identify depressive disorders, the screening cut off point at 30 days for the MCS was 45.6; 44.5

for the RAND-12 scoring; and 40.2 for the BRP-12 scoring system. No statistically significant differences between the three scoring methods were found. Citing the study by Gill et al. (2007) and their findings, the authors suggest that the SF12 could be a useful screening instrument when assessing for depression in the general population (Vilagut et al., 2013).

By understanding the components of the SF12, such as the Mental Component Summary (MCS) score, a nurse may be able to identify patients at risk for mental health problems, such as depression or anxiety, and the patient's perception about how these symptoms affect daily activities. This information can provide additional clues to the clinician about the patient's feelings and functioning. Early identification of a problem at the beginning of a cardiac rehabilitation program would allow the nurse to implement care strategies and better support patients' needs during their participation.

METHODS

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive, retrospective design to describe the mental health in a population of cardiac patients, identify factors associated with mental health problems, and assess the effect of cardiac rehabilitation (CR) on mental health to answer the research questions. Existing data from patients who participated in a CR program between 2008 and 2010 were analyzed. Cardiac rehabilitation nurses collected the patient demographics and SF12 data during the initial consultation visit, and again at the completion of a 12-week CR program. The data were entered into a computerized charting system called Patient Analysis Tracking System (PATS). This system contains the software with which to calculate the Mental Component Summary (MCS) score from the SF12 data that had been entered into the PATS system.

Setting and Sample

The CR program was located at an outpatient center associated with an urban hospital facility in Southern California. The convenience sample included all patients enrolled between 2008-2010 with complete baseline demographic data, and SF12 survey data. Patients with incomplete demographic data were excluded, as well as patients who had not completed the SF12. The diagnosis variables of myocardial infarction (MI); myocardial infarction with percutaneous transluminal coronary angioplasty (PTCA), or stent; heart failure and cardiomyopathy; and cardiac surgery were categorized for frequencies and then subsequent evaluation. The surgical category included patients who were completing the CR program after experiencing either a valvular surgical repair or replacement, or a coronary artery bypass grafting surgical procedure.

Patients entering the CR program routinely begin three to four weeks after their cardiac diagnosis or intervention, with variations due to each individual patient's health status and preferences of the prescribing physician. At the first visit, all patients are interviewed by a registered nurse. At that time, demographic data were collected and the SF12 questionnaire administered. The CR administrative assistant and the nurse input this data into the Patient Analysis Tracking System (PATS). The CR program is 36 visits in duration, and patients are scheduled three times a week for twelve weeks, except for holidays and other missed days. Any missed session may be added to the end of the program so each patient completes 36 visits.

Data Collection Instrument

The Short Form 12 (SF12) is a twelve question, shortened form of the Short Form-36 (SF36), a 36-item questionnaire used extensively to evaluate patients' perspectives on their health and quality of life. The shorter SF12 can be self-administered within two minutes, which allows for ease of use in various clinical patient populations. This tool measures the patient's quality of life over the previous four-week period prior to the completion of the survey (Ware et al., 1996).

The SF12 has established reliability and validity both within and outside cardiovascular populations. This questionnaire has been used in patients with diabetes, total knee replacement surgery, and other chronic diseases (Carsten, Ehlebracht-Konig, Kuhn, & Bullinger, 2006; Clement, MacDonald, Burnett, & Breusch, 2013).

Comparative studies suggest that the SF12 reproduced more than 90% of variance of the SF36 in both the physical and mental component summary scores (Ware et al., 1996). Ware et al. (1996) evaluated the reliability of the SF12 using the test-retest, and

two-week correlations. The authors found correlations of 0.76 for the MCS scores from the SF12, when compared to the MCS scores from the SF36. In addition, twenty tests for empirical validity were done for the SF36 and results were replicated with the SF12. Another study supporting the use of the SF12 as the shorter version of the SF36 confirmed that the scores could be used to assess both physical and mental areas and closely replicate data obtained by the longer SF36 version (Failde, Medina, Ramirez, & Arana, 2009).

The SF12 is patented by QualityMetric (QM), and the interpretation of this questionnaire is completed using a complex algorithm. This algorithm can be easily done using computer software purchased from QM. The QM website describes the certified scoring system software, such as the Enterprise, which can be used to analyze data for organizations that wish to collect and manage data within their own software system (QualityMetric, 2014). The hospital facility providing the data for this study purchased such a system, and used it to analyze data during the years 2008-2010.

The SF12 version two (SF12v.2) health survey is very similar to the original SF12, with “increased range and precision for the Role-Physical and Role-Emotional scales, improved wording, and easier-to-use format” (Ware, Kosinski, & Keller, 2007, p. 29). The SF12v2 was the questionnaire used in this study. Both versions of the SF12 and also the SF36 have twelve items covering eight different dimensions of health: physical functioning, role-physical and role- emotional, pain, general health, vitality, social functioning, and mental health (Windsor, Rodgers, Butterworth, Anstey, & Jorm, 2006). These eight areas are computed into two summary scores, the Physical Component Summary (PCS) score and the Mental Component Summary (MCS) score by a complex

algorithm calculation, which as previously mentioned, can be done using a purchased computer software system. For the purposes of this project, only the MCS scores were used to answer the research questions.

The SF12 accurately assesses the patients' ratings of their limitations of daily activities, due to both physical and psychological health during the previous four weeks prior to survey completion (Ware et al., 1996). The range of scores on the SF12 are between zero to 100, with the mean score for all scales on both the SF12 and SF36, being 50 with a standard deviation of 10. The authors of the SF12 and SF36 created a norm-based scoring system by calculating each scale within both instruments so each would be interpreted on the same 0-100 range, with the mean of 50. If an individual's PCS or MCS score is less than 45, or an aggregate score is less than 47, the data can be interpreted as below average (Ware, Snow, & Kosinski, 1993). The higher scores reflect a higher perception of health in either scale, and the higher the score, the greater the level of the patient's health in the area scored (Ware et al., 1996; Ware et al., 1993).

In this study, the cut-off score used from the MCS was less than 45 for depressed samples, and 45 and higher for the non-depressed samples. The authors of the SF12, Ware et al. (1996), described scores of less than 45 to be considered as less than normal for all scales within the SF12 questionnaire. Vilagut et al. (2013) determined that 45.6 was an accurate score to use for depression screening when compared with other depression instruments, and Gill et al. (2007) used 45 and higher as a cut-off score for both depression and anxiety screening. As a conservative measure, the lower score of 45 identified by Ware et al. (1996) was used.

Data Processing and Analysis

Institutional Review Board (IRB) approvals were obtained from both the hospital and University, and the data extracted from the PATS database by a representative from the facility. Prior to the data being provided to the researcher, all patient identifiers were removed. The demographic data collected included the age, gender, and cardiac diagnosis, or interventional procedure for all patients who participated in CR between 2008 and 2010. The MCS and demographic data were provided to the researcher in an Excel file loaded onto a flash drive to enable easier uploading of the data to a Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 for analysis. Descriptive analyses, including measures of central tendency (means, ranges, standard deviations, percentages) were calculated on the sample of patients with complete demographic data who had filled out the SF12 prior to starting the CR program. Patients that did not complete the SF12 after discharge from the program were not included in the analysis to compare the two scores from pre and post CR participation.

Appropriate statistical tests were performed to examine the data for relationships between the demographic and clinical variables with the MCS scores. The baseline MCS scores were also summarized and compared to the MCS scores collected after the completion of the CR program to determine the answer to the research question related to the effect of participation in CR on the sample of patient participants.

Ethical Considerations

All original data files were only accessible to the researcher. The facility research personnel removed patient identifiers prior to data being provided. The researcher kept the de-identified data on a flash drive for analysis, and all data were deleted from the

flash drive once data was uploaded onto personal computer. The researcher's personal computer is loaded with anti-virus software and is password protected. The computer has been kept in either a locked office or at the researcher's home. All data analysis was performed only on this computer. Assistance in data analysis was provided by both a California State University and another university faculty member on the researcher's personal computer as approved by the IRB. All data will be destroyed after one year from the completion of the project (anticipated June 2015). Because this is a retrospective review of data, individual patient consent was not required. However, all participants signed a general hospital consent releasing their data, if de-identified, only for purposes of research.

Project Implementation

The scope of the project is limited to one CR program in a hospital in California. Potential benefits include a greater awareness of nurses and other staff about patients at risk for mental health issues that may not have been identified during a regular visit. The hope is that this awareness might provide better insight so that staff members can enhance assessment, refer patients to resources, provide a more focused, individualized plan of care, and more carefully monitor patients who are at risk.

Stakeholders

The potential stakeholders for this project include patients, administrators, and clinicians. Patients with low MCS scores may be at risk for depression and would be identified early in their CR program. These patients would be carefully monitored during CR visits. Currently, any cardiac patient at this facility may have access to a meeting with a social worker in addition to care by the nursing staff. The potential for additional

required services of a social worker may be identified by this study. The optional visit with the social worker would be strongly encouraged for patients at risk, and follow-up done. Patient characteristics associated with low mental well-being will be identified and shared with the CR staff so they will be alerted to patients that may have mental health issues.

RESULTS

The patient data received from the cardiac research nurse at the facility included 668 subjects. However, due to a large amount of missing data, many patients were not included. Table 1 displays the demographic characteristics of the sample ($n = 306$). Of the patients that participated in cardiac rehabilitation (CR) during 2008-2010 ($n = 668$), 362 patients were excluded. There were six excluded due to missing diagnosis, one was excluded due to a missing age, and the rest ($n = 355$) were excluded due to incomplete baseline data on the SF12 prior to beginning the program. The remaining patient sample data ($n = 306$) were analyzed using descriptive statistics to identify the sample characteristics. T-test and chi-square tests were used to examine associations between the independent and the dependent variables.

The study sample was generally middle-aged and older (mean age 67.4 years), and primarily male (73.9%). The diagnoses and interventional procedures were separated into categories. Of the total sample, 38.6% had undergone a cardiac surgical procedure, and 25.2% had experienced either a percutaneous transluminal coronary angioplasty (PTCA) or stent, with another 21.2% experiencing a myocardial infarction in addition to having a PTCA or stent. Patients that experienced only a MI without an interventional procedure were 8.5% of this population. An additional 6.5% of patients had a diagnosis of heart failure (Table 1).

Research Question 1: What is the mental health status among a population of cardiac patients participating in a cardiac rehabilitation program?

Of the sample, some patients only completed the SF12 prior to beginning the CR program, and did not complete this questionnaire after discharge from the program ($n =$

91). These patients were included in the analysis to determine the prevalence of patients who screened positive for depression in this sample; however, they were not included for evaluation of the effect of CR on mental health status. Of the sample, only six patients scored between 45 and 45.97, and were included in the non-depressed category. After analysis, 24.8% of patients in this sample scored below 45 and were subsequently identified as screening positive for depression. The lowest MCS score in this sample was 15.87, and the highest score was 72.74.

Research Question 2: What factors are associated with mental health problems in a cardiac patient population?

Table 1 outlines the results of analysis performed on data collected at baseline ($n = 306$) to determine if there was a difference across demographic factors that may be associated with low MCS scores in this cardiac patient population. At baseline, patient clinical and demographic attributes did not differ between patients with $MCS < 45$ and $MCS \geq 45$. Of the 76 patients that screened positive for depression, 67.1% were male, and 32.9% were female. However, this was not statistically significant ($p = .12$). In addition, the percentage of males in the total sample population was 73.9%, as compared to the 26.1% that were female.

Table 1

Comparison of Baseline MCS-12 Scores by Demographics (n = 306)

Sample Characteristics	Total	MCS Score ^a		p ^b
	N = 306	< 45 N = 76 (24.8%)	≥ 45 N = 230 (75.2%)	
Age <i>M (SD)</i>	67.44 (10.46)	66.50 (10.59)	67.76 (10.42)	.37
Gender				
Male	226 (73.9%)	51 (67.1%)	175 (76.1%)	.12
Female	80 (26.1%)	25 (32.9%)	55 (23.9%)	
MI				
Yes	26 (8.5%)	8 (10.5%)	18 (7.8%)	.46
No		68 (89.5%)	212 (92.2%)	
MI/PTCA/Stent				
Yes	65 (21.2%)	18 (23.7%)	47 (20.4%)	.55
No		58 (76.3%)	183 (79.6%)	
PTCA/Stent				
Yes	77 (25.2%)	18 (23.7%)	59 (25.7%)	.73
No		58 (76.3%)	171 (74.3%)	
Surgery				
Yes	118 (38.6%)	26 (34.2%)	92 (40.0%)	.37
No		50 (65.8%)	138 (60.0%)	
Heart Failure				
Yes	20 (6.5%)	6 (7.9%)	14 (6.1%)	.58
No		70 (92.1%)	216 (93.9%)	

Note. PTCA = Percutaneous Transluminal Coronary Angioplasty. MI = Myocardial Infarction.

^aReported as mean (SD) or frequency (valid %) where appropriate.

^bReported for independent samples t-tests or chi-square tests of independence where appropriate.

Research Question 3: What is the effect of participation in a cardiac rehabilitation program on mental health?

Analysis of patient data with a one-group pre and post design was performed to evaluate the impact of participation in the CR program on the MCS scores collected prior to and after discharge ($n = 215$). In this sample, 91 (30%) patients did not complete a post-SF12 questionnaire, and these patients were excluded from this final analysis. A paired samples t-test revealed a statistically significant difference in the MCS scores of the patients providing data both before ($M_{\text{MCS Pretest}} = 51.25$, $SD = 10.15$) and after participation in the CR program ($M_{\text{MCS Posttest}} = 53.79$, $SD = 8.48$; $t(214) = -3.87$, $p < .001$). Additionally, it was verified that for the 215 patients that were analyzed, all completed the 36 visits of the program.

While examination of the effect size reveals only a small improvement in scores (Cohen's $D = .26$), examination of the number of patients classified as depressed (MCS score < 45) reveals a statistically significant increase in the MCS scores collected after completing the CR program. Specifically, a chi-square test of independence revealed that by the end of the CR program, 33 (60.0%) of the participants who were initially classified as depressed at baseline (MCS < 45) were no longer classified as depressed (MCS score ≥ 45) at posttest, while only 12 (7.5%) of participants who had screened as non-depressed (MCS ≥ 45) were classified as depressed at posttest, $\chi^2(1) = 32.47$, $p < .001$.

DISCUSSION

Mental Health Status in Cardiac Patient Population

The purpose of this study was to describe mental health in a population of cardiac patients, identify factors associated with mental health problems, and examine the effect of cardiac rehabilitation (CR) on mental health. No statistically significant factors were identified to have an effect on mental health in this sample. However, this project suggests that CR has a positive influence on mental health in a cardiac population.

The analysis of demographic data collected revealed that 76 (24.8%) patients out of 306 were screened as depressed using the MCS score of less than 45 at baseline screening. The patients that scored 45 or higher, representing non-depressed ($n = 230$), were 75.2% of the total sample. Those that had lower MCS scores were 24.8% of the total sample, and screened positive for depression. These findings are similar to results found in other studies that identified depression in about 20% of patients with cardiac disease (Frasure-Smith & Lesperance, 2008; Lesperance & Frasure-Smith, 2000; Milani & Lavie, 2007).

Factors Associated with Mental Health Problems

No significant relationship between the demographic factors of age, gender, cardiac diagnosis or procedure, and mental health status were identified. Of the total sample ($n = 306$), 80 were females and 226 were male. However, it is interesting to note that of the total number of patients identified as depressed ($n = 76$), 51 were males (67.1%) and 25 were females (31.3%). When comparing the number of depressed women ($n = 25$) to the total number of females in the sample, 31.25% of the women

were identified as depressed. Similarly, in comparing the number of males in the sample, 51 (22.5%) of the males in this study were identified as depressed. This study is also aligned with other studies that suggest females have a higher incidence of depression than males in the cardiac patient population (Doering et al., 2007; Doering et al., 2011; Frasure-Smith & Lesperance, 2008; Grace et al., 2008; Hunt-Shanks et al., 2009; Rutledge et al., 2012). Women that have had coronary artery bypass grafting have also been shown to experience higher rates of depression than men that have this same procedure (Doering et al., 2007). Although in this study sample, neither the patients' gender nor their diagnoses or interventional procedures were associated with the incidence of depression when using the MCS score of < 45 as a screening tool. In contrast, a study by Blumenthal et al. (2003) revealed that 38% of patients were identified as depressed after coronary artery bypass grafting ($n = 817$).

Age was found to have no significant association with screening for depression in this sample. Studies evaluating the influence of age on depression in cardiac patients have had varied results. Murphy et al. (2008) found no significant age differences in patterns of depression. However, other research found that younger patients had higher depression and/or anxiety levels as compared to older patients (Blumenthal et al., 2003; Elderon et al., 2011; Frasure-Smith & Lesperance, 2008). Since the mean age of the sample was 67.4 years, many patients may have been retired, and therefore had less job stress and responsibilities in this aggregate sample. In addition, this CR program is in a location considered by many to be affluent, and the possibility exists that less financial stress for many in this population could have had an effect. It is also possible that the

large number of excluded patients (54.1%) that did not complete the SF12 questionnaire may have altered the results of the analysis ($n = 362$).

Effect of Participation in Cardiac Rehabilitation

The primary finding of this study was that participants who screened as depressed at baseline showed improvement in depression scores at the completion of CR. In the literature, CR has been shown to have a positive influence in improving depression in cardiac patients (Blumenthal et al., 2012; Frank et al., 2011; Shepherd & While, 2012). Although only a small increase in the mean MCS score was seen after completion of the program, the increase was statistically significant. Using the MCS score from the SF12 as a tool to screen for depression may provide additional input into understanding the patient's perspective on their quality of life. The use of this questionnaire allows the patient to communicate thoughts and beliefs about their symptoms and the effect on their life.

Cardiac rehabilitation programs provide education, emotional and social support, and progressive exercise and strengthening. Exercise alone may have a positive effect on mental health (Blumenthal et al., 2003; Hunt-Shanks et al., 2009; Milani & Lavie, 2007). However, the education provided may allow patients to feel empowered to make changes to improve their own health which may contribute to mental well-being. Beckie et al. (2011) identified that social support between patients participating in a gender-tailored program had an increased benefit on depression scores and motivational behavior. Frasure-Smith et al. (2000) identified that patients who were found to have strong social support had a lower incidence of depression. This is significant as depression was identified to be a predictor of mortality one year after MI in this study.

Participation in CR has been shown to promote healthy lifestyle changes in diet and exercise even after completion of the program (Beckie et al., 2011; Scotto et al., 2011). Yohannes et al. (2010) demonstrated that there may be long-term benefits of CR on quality of life, depression, anxiety levels, and physical activity up to 12 months after discharge from the program. At the initial CR session, the nurses assess the patient's perceptions and interpretations of symptoms to help plan care strategies. Screening for depression may better assist the nurse to assess patients at risk for depression.

Identifying and providing resources for these patients may benefit their future cardiac health, as depression has been shown to be associated with worsening cardiac disease. If depression is untreated in the cardiac patient, they may continue to be depressed even 12 months after their cardiac diagnosis or event. In one study of patients with coronary heart disease, approximately half of patients with minor depression had improved symptoms, but 42% remained depressed or had a recurrence of depression within the 12 months following their cardiac event (Hance, Carney, Freedland, & Skala, 1996).

Limitations

First and foremost, this study was cross sectional in design, and lacking a control group. Thus, one can only identify associations between the independent and the dependent variables and cannot establish causation. In addition, data provided to the researcher from the facility were limited, and given without patient identifiers. This prevented further analysis of the data, including the presence of co-morbid conditions, such as a previous history of depression. In addition, medication history was unavailable, so it could not be determined if antidepressant medications were taken either prior to or during the duration of the CR program. Demographic data such as

marital status, educational history, ethnicity, were also not provided, so these factors could not be analyzed. This information may have had an effect on the statistical analysis of the data as the literature suggests these factors may have an association with depression (Milani et al., 1996).

Although the original sample provided to the researcher consisted of data from 668 patients, missing data, including a lack of SF12 data, resulted in a much smaller sample of patients than anticipated ($n = 306$). These results might have been altered due to the sample size that was analyzed compared to the original sample that was quite large ($n = 668$). The SF12 questionnaire was either not completed or results not recorded during the years 2008-2010, so 362 patients were excluded from the analysis. The additional 91 patients who did not complete the SF12 at the end of the program, were then also excluded from the analysis of the effect of CR on mental health, so an even smaller sample was analyzed ($n = 215$). These excluded patients that did not complete the post-CR SF12 were included in the chi-square analysis to examine the association of demographic data and MCS depression scores and to answer research question numbers one and two (Table 1).

Since the data analyzed were from 2008-2010, procedural changes and improvements implemented over the last four years may have made an impact on the amount of complete data collected. The CR program has grown substantially, and has been relocated offsite at a location near the hospital with a large, attractive gym. In addition, the older data may limit the generalization of the results to the current patients at this facility. More current data may have revealed different results. Since the study

was a convenience sample at one hospital in Southern California, generalization to other cardiac patient populations may be limited.

Future Studies

A more in-depth analysis of patient data that include patient identifiers may provide additional insights into other potential influencing factors on cardiac patients' mental health. Factors such as co-morbid conditions, medications that may cause depression as a side effect, history of either treated or untreated depression, marital status, social isolation, financial strain, or employment should be explored. Turner et al. (2010) identified that patients who were employed prior to a cardiac diagnosis or procedure may have increased anxiety and depression due a possible inability to continue a normal work routine due to changes in their health status. These additional factors may have had some confounding influence on the results of this current study.

Additional research may include analysis of an association between the patients' physical strength, stamina, and physical well-being and mental health status. Specific activity levels achieved could be compared to patients' mental health scores. Assessment of anxiety with depression may also be critical. The MCS score was identified by Gill et al. (2007) to recognize both anxiety and depression for scores 45 and less. It may be difficult to accurately assess depression alone in the presence of anxiety without further evaluation beyond the low MCS score.

As the SF12 is considered a quality of life questionnaire, only a few studies have identified its use as a screening tool for depression. Future research on the use of the MCS score is needed to evaluate accuracy in screening for depression. In addition, the cut-off score has not been consistent. Studies identifying the most accurate cut-off score

should be further explored. For example, Ware et al. (1996) identified a score of less than 45 as abnormal (low), and Vilagut et al. (2013) used 45.6 and lower as screening for depression, while Gill et al. (2007) used 45 and less to screen for both anxiety and depression. Further research may provide a more consistent cut-off score and should be explored.

Recommendations for Nursing Practice Change

Currently, the CR department at the study facility has a social worker available for eight hours per week. All patients are offered the opportunity for an evaluation during the initial admission interview to the CR program. Documentation procedures that identify which patients have seen the social worker have been inconsistent. Patients have been responsible to book the appointment should they want to be evaluated. The staff has not followed up with these patients. In addition, patients may forget that this service is available to them due to the large volume of information given during the initial CR intake visit. Ensuring that at-risk patients receive this benefit may result in planning better strategies to improve patients' mental health status. Better documentation about the frequency of these evaluations may show a need for additional hours required for the social worker consultation service.

At this study facility, patient data are kept in the Patient Analysis and Tracking System (PATS), and this system contains the software to analyze the MCS from the SF12. If the SF12 data are not uploaded into the PATS system, the MCS score is not calculated. The electronic medical records system used to document each visit is a completely different software program than PATS. If the nurse does not access the PATS system for the MCS score, this info was completed, the researcher has discussed

procedures to ensure the documentation of the MCS score on the patients' kardex with the director and nurses. If patients are found to have depressive symptoms, the nurse will have the opportunity to provide resources for further assessment, identify individual needs, and direct care. Additional social and emotional support interventions during CR sessions may be made available. Since cardiac patients who are depressed are at greater risk for future cardiovascular problems, identifying depression may make a significant difference in their health.

Currently, nurses working in the CR department only look at the patients' responses to one question from the SF12. This question asks specifically about the effect of emotional problems, such as depression or anxiety, on the performance of regular activities over the previous four weeks. The available responses allow the patient to choose one of five scores to rate how much they have been affected (Ware et al., 1996). From this response, the nurses assess if a patient may be depressed. The MCS score on the rest of the SF12 have not been included in the assessment. The nurses have never been educated about the interpreting the results of this questionnaire, even though it is collected on nearly every patient. Educating the CR nurses about the importance of the MCS score as a screening tool may impact the assessment of patients' mental health status, and may help plan individual care strategies aimed to benefit mental health. In addition, instead of the SF12 being an optional assessment tool, nurses might encourage each patient to complete it offering information about the benefits resulting from the instrument data.

Nurses caring for cardiac patients in the hospital units may be unaware of the high incidence of depression following a cardiac event. In this hospital facility, there is

no standard procedure or protocol related to screening of mental health issues for the cardiac population. However, there is a procedure to screen for postpartum depression. Creating a protocol to assess hospitalized patients may identify individuals at risk by educating them and providing support during both their hospital stay and home. The American Heart Association in 2008 recommended a two-question screening tool, the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-2) for routine depression screening (Lichtman et al., 2008). The questions ask the patient about any lack of interest or pleasure in doing things, and feelings of hopelessness, depression, or feeling down over the previous two weeks. This two question screening tool may be beneficial to identify patients at risk, and require little time for the nurse to perform while the patient is still in the hospital.

At this hospital facility, only about one third of eligible patients that might benefit from CR are currently referred by their physician. Some patients that are referred do not complete the entire program due to the high co-payment required for each of the 36 visits during the 12 weeks. Education about the benefits of CR and knowledge of the CR program may increase patient referrals if physicians, nurses, patients and families were more aware of the benefits, including the effect on mental health.

Shepherd and While (2012) reported that patients who were given a plan of progressive exercise and provided resources for an in-home CR program had similar benefits to those who participated at a CR center program. Currently, CR nurses are providing education on admission to patients with a cardiac diagnosis or event. No post-discharge follow-up on patients that do not enroll in CR is being conducted by the facility; however, each patient receives a letter notifying them of their eligibility to participate in a CR program. If patients are admitted to the hospital for a cardiac event,

over the weekend or holiday, these patients may not receive the educational materials and other information from the CR nurse as the CR department is closed in the evenings, and on weekends and holidays. Education for nurses who work with cardiac patients may allow for more consistency in providing this information to patients and families. Promotion of the importance of home exercise, diet, and other education may be viewed as too time consuming by the nurses working on the units. However, if the nurses were made aware of the benefits and received education regarding the high incidence of depression in this population, they may more actively participate in teaching this information.

The director of the cardiac units and the director of cardiac outpatient services need to be involved with planning changes based on the information found in this project. The director of cardiac outpatient services suggested this study as a project for the researcher, and would be interested in implementing CR promotion to the nurses and other involved care providers. The researcher has presented information to the Nursing Research Council, and has been asked to present at a hospital conference in the future on this topic to provide information to nurses caring for this population. Educating nurses may encourage participation in advocating the CR program for their patients. Screening for depression in this patient population may also help individuals get the resources they need to reach their highest level of health.

Significance of Study

The study is significant because mental health issues, such as, anxiety and depression occur frequently among cardiac patients. In addition, the literature suggests that mental health problems, such as depression, may worsen cardiac disease, increase

mortality, and affect quality of life. Identifying patients at risk for depression may improve individual assessment and interventions that could improve cardiovascular health.

Cardiac rehabilitation staff members have opportunities to make a difference in a patient's quality of life by carefully evaluating mental health issues and refer to appropriate providers. In addition, CR nurses may have opportunities to make adjustments in a patient's program based on specific needs, and identify what may benefit each individual in building awareness of depression, the consequences, and how to support patients during participation in a CR program.

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